

Copper(II) and Nickel (II) Complexes of Neutral Tetradentate Schiff Bases[†]

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Several hydrolytically stable copper (II) and nickel (II) complexes of neutral tetradentate Schiff bases derived by the condensation of 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol with 2-formyl pyridine (=FPTN and FPTNOL) and 2-acetylpyridine (=APTN and APTNOL) have been synthesized. The complexes have been characterised by electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibilities, infrared spectra, molar conductivities and elemental analyses. All of these complexes contain a 1:1 ratio of tetradentate ligand to metal (II) salt.

Copper (II) complexes of the type $[Cu(L)]ClO_4$ are found to be five-coordinate, while $[Cu(L)](ClO_4)_2$ complexes are tetragonal or square planar in structure. The infrared spectra of the copper (II) and nickel (II) complexes support the Schiff base formulation of the ligands and provide evidence for the coordination of the pyridyl groups. A tetragonal crystal field model provides a basis for the interpretation of the visible and near infrared electronic spectra of nickel (II) complexes with the tetradentate ligands occupying the square planar arrangement. The complexes $Ni(L)X_2 \cdot nH_2O$, where $L = FPTN, FPTNOL, APTN, APTNOL$; $X = Cl, NO_2$ or NCS , behave as 2:1 electrolytes in aqueous solution and give rise to a common species $[Ni(L)(H_2O)_2]^{2+}$. In aqueous solution the complex ion $[Ni(L)(H_2O)_2]^{2+}$ reacts with neutral monodentate donors to yield $[Ni(L)(donor)_2]^{2+}$.

RECENTLY we have reported some copper (II) and nickel (II) complexes of neutral bidentate Schiff bases.¹⁻⁴ In continuation of our work we have isolated some copper (II) and nickel (II) complexes of neutral tetradentate Schiff bases derived by the condensation of 2-formylpyridine with trimethylenediamine (=FPTN), 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (=FPTNOL) and also of the Schiff bases derived by the condensation of 2-acetylpyridine with trimethylenediamine (=APTN) and 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (=APTNOL). A recent publication⁵ on the nickel (II) complexes of FPTN, FPTNOL and APTN prompted us to report our results. This paper describes the preparation, properties and structural elucidation of some copper (II) and nickel (II) complexes of the above mentioned four ligands. Previous studies⁶⁻¹⁰ of the ionic transition metal complexes of neutral, tetradentate Schiff bases have dealt primarily with the ligands derived from ethylenediamine and pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (=FPEN), or quinoline-8-aldehyde (=QAEN).

Experimental :

Elemental analyses, measurements of magnetic susceptibilities, infrared spectra, molar conductances, etc. were done as described previously.^{1,1}

Preparation of the complexes :

Copper (II) complexes, $Cu(L)(ClO_4)_2$ (where, $L = FPTN, (I)$; $APTN, (III)$; $FPTNOL, (V)$; and $APTNOL, (VII)$) : An ethanol solution of the ligand was prepared from a mixture of 2-formylpyridine (0.02 mole) or 2-acetylpyridine and 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (0.01 mole) in ethanol (25 ml), which was heated on water-bath (1 hr) and then di-

luted with to 300 ml. This solution was then added slowly to a stirred ethanol solution (50 ml) of copper perchlorate hexahydrate (10.0 g). The dark green compound was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo.

$[Cu(L)]ClO_4$ (where, $L = FPTN, (II)$; $L = APTN, (IV)$; $FPTNOL, (VI)$; and $APTNOL, (VIII)$) : The solution of the above complexes, e. g., $Cu(FPTN)(ClO_4)_2$ (0.05 g) in acetonitrile (50 ml) was treated with a solution of tetraethylammonium iodide (0.25 g) in acetonitrile (10 ml) and the mixture was evaporated on a water-bath (15 ml). This solution, on keeping in a refrigerator, gave dark green crystals, which was filtered off, washed with acetonitrile, and dried in vacuo.

Nickel (II) Complexes, $Ni(L)Cl_2 \cdot nH_2O$ (where, $L = FPTN, (IX)$; $APTN, (XI)$; $FPTNOL, (XII)$; and $APTNOL, (XIV)$; $n = 0$ or 1) : 2-Formylpyridine or 2-acetylpyridine (50 m mole) dissolved in 10 ml of isopropyl alcohol was added dropwise to a solution of diamine (25 m mole) in 10-15 ml of the same solvent, which previously cooled to $\sim 0^\circ$. The resulting solution was stirred at room temperature for 1-2 hr. (In some cases refluxing is necessary at this stage); and then added to a hot solution of nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate (25 m mole) in 80 ml of absolute ethanol. After slow evaporation to 50-70 ml followed by cooling, green crystals were obtained. These were filtered, washed with isopropyl alcohol, and dried in vacuo at $\sim 60^\circ$.

For the complex (XI) about 30 ml of n-butylalcohol was added in the reaction mixture and slowly evaporated to get the desired complex, which was washed with water-ethanol-butanol mixture.

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For the complexes (XII) and (XIV), the $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in large excess of absolute ethanol was boiled (~2hrs.) with ~ 100 ml of 2,2-dimethoxypropane prior to the addition to the ligand solutions. The rest of the procedure was same as described above.

Ni(L)(X)_2 (where, $L=\text{FPTN}$ & $X=\text{NO}_2$, (X); $L=\text{FPTNOL}$ & $X=\text{NCS}$, (XIII); and $L=\text{APTNO}$ & $X=\text{NO}_2$, (XV): The metathesis of the chloro-complex with appropriate sodium salts in methanol gave these three chelates as red or brown crystals.

Result and Discussion

Copper (II) complexes: The copper (II) complexes are quite stable in air. The analytical data (Table 1) reveal a 1:1 ratio of Schiff base ligand to metal ratio for all of the complexes. The conductivities of (I), (III), (V), and (VII) in nitromethane are all in the usual range for 2 : 1 electrolytes in this solvent (Table 2). On the otherhand, the conductivities of (II), (IV), (VI) and (VIII) are all in the usual range for 1 : 1 electrolytes in the same solvent (Table 2).

All the compounds of the type $[\text{Cu(L)I}]\text{ClO}_4$ possibly have a five-coordinate structure in the solid and in solutions of nitromethane as revealed from their

electronic spectral data (Table 3). Analogous five-coordinate geometry has also been proposed for a series of copper (II) chelates of the type $[\text{Cu(FPEN)L}]^+$ ($L=\text{Br, I}$)^{3,9}. However, it is difficult to say the types of distorted geometry these chelates will adopt without X-ray crystallographic study. It may be mentioned that bromomethoxy-compound, $[\text{Cu(FPEN, ROH)Br}]\text{ClO}_4$, has been shown to have the five-coordinate structure by a single crystal three-dimensional X-ray structural determination.^{1,2} However, the structure of this compound is grossly distorted from either of the regular five-coordinate geometries. Such "intermediate" geometries appear to be quite common feature of five-coordinate metal-chelate complexes.^{1,9} The analogous structures may be proposed for the present copper (II) chelates $[\text{Cu(L)I}]\text{ClO}_4$.

The copper (II) complexes $\text{Cu(L)(ClO}_4)_2$ (Table 1) show a single relatively sharp absorption band in the spectra of these chelates at ~ 16,500 cm^{-1} (Table 3), which closely resembles that in the tetramine copper (II) compounds, which have a tetragonal (4+2) geometry. Perchlorate ions in these chelates are found to be ionic (infrared data, very slightly split band around 1000-1150 cm^{-1}). Accordingly, these compounds are

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF CU (II) AND NI (II) CHELATES

Complex	Found %		Calcd. %	
	Cu/Ni	N	Cu/Ni	N
$\text{Cu(FPTN)(ClO}_4)_2$, (I)	12.85	11.20	12.34	10.88
$[\text{Cu(FPTN)I}]\text{ClO}_4$, (II)	11.58	10.45	11.71	10.33
$\text{Cu(APTN)(ClO}_4)_2$, (III)	11.45	10.12	11.70	10.32
$[\text{Cu(APTN)I}]\text{ClO}_4$, (IV)	10.98	10.12	11.14	9.82
$\text{Cu(FPTNOL)(ClO}_4)_2$, (V)	12.00	10.82	11.97	10.56
$[\text{Cu(FPTNOL)I}]\text{ClO}_4$, (VI)	11.25	9.88	11.39	10.03
$\text{Cu(APTNOL)(ClO}_4)_2$, (VII)	11.41	10.22	11.37	10.02
$[\text{Cu(APTNOL)I}]\text{ClO}_4$, (VIII)	10.38	9.29	10.83	9.55
$\text{Ni(FPTN)Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, (IX)	14.80	13.99	14.53	14.04
$\text{Ni(FPTN)(NO}_2)_2$, (X)	11.60	21.05	11.47	20.89
Ni(APTN)Cl_2 , (XI)	14.59	13.82	14.18	13.70
Ni(FPTNOL)Cl_2 , (XII)	14.00	13.98	14.61	14.10
Ni(FPTNOL)(NCS)_2 , (XIII)	13.34	18.85	13.12	19.01
Ni(APTNOL)Cl_2 , (XIV)	13.80	13.48	13.65	13.17
$\text{Ni(APTNOL)(NO}_2)_2$, (XV)	12.79	18.21	13.00	18.84

TABLE 2—MOLECULAR CONDUCTIVITIES AT 25°C AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS

No.	Molecular conductivity ^a		Magnetic moment		
	Solvent	$\Lambda^{\text{M}}\text{b}$	Electrolytic nature	T°K	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
I	CH_3NO_2	164	2:1	298	1.85
II	CH_3NO_2	88	1:1	300	1.90
III	CH_3NO_2	168	2:1	298	1.88
IV	CH_3NO_2	90	1:1	298	1.82
V	CH_3NO_2	168	2:1	298	1.92
VI	CH_3NO_2	92	1:1	300	1.88
VII	CH_3NO_2	160	2:1	300	1.92
VIII	CH_3NO_2	82	1:1	300	1.90
IX	H_2O	190	2:1	298	3.20
	CH_3OH	88	1:1	—	—
X	H_2O	180	2:1	298	3.09
XI	H_2O	188	2:1	298	3.23
	CH_3OH	90	1:1	—	—
XII	H_2O	188	2:1	300	3.22
XIII	C	—	—	300	3.30
XIV	H_2O	192	2:1	300	3.20
XV	H_2O	198	2:1	300	3.19

a) of 10^{-3}M solutions; b) $\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$; c) Not measured.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complex	Solvent	Band position in KK (log ϵ mol)
Cu (FPTN)(ClO ₄) ₂ , (I)	CH ₃ NO ₂	16.5 (1.95)
[Cu (FPTN) I] ClO ₄ , (II)	CH ₃ NO ₂	13.0 (2.29)
Cu (FPTNOL)(ClO ₄) ₂ , (V)	CH ₃ NO ₂	16.55 (1.88)
[Cu(FPTNO)I] ClO ₄ , (VI)	CH ₃ NO ₂	12.95 (2.18)
Ni (FPTN)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O, (IX)	Nujolmull	9.0, 11.98 (sh), 13.0, 17.5 (sh), 26.5(sh), 32.0, 33.7 (sh), 40.0.
	H ₂ O	10.0 (sh), 12.5 (1.0), 13.2 (0.9), 18.5(0.8)
Ni (FPTN) (NO ₂) ₂ , (X)	Nujolmull	12.5, 30.0 (sh), 33.0, 40.0.
	H ₂ O	10.1 (0.5), 12.8 (1.2), 13.5(1.0), 19.0 (0.9).
Ni (APTN)Cl ₂ (XI)	H ₂ O	9.8(0.48), 12.8 (0.9), 13.5 (0.9), 17.8 (sh), 19.5 (0.7).
Ni (FPTNOL) Cl ₂ , (XII)	Nujolmull	9.2, 11.09, 12.7, 17.8 (sh), 31.9, 39.5.
Ni (FPTNOL)(NCS) ₂ , (XIII)	Nujolmull	11.3, 12.8 (sh), 18.6, 32.5, 40.0(sh).
Ni (APTNOL) Cl ₂ , (XIV),	H ₂ O	9.7(0.5), 13.0(1.0), 13.5(0.9), 17.6(sh), 19.5 (0.6).
Ni (APTNOL)(NO ₂) ₂ , (XV)	Nujolmull	12.6, 31.2 (sh), 33.0, 40.00
	H ₂ O	10.3(0.7), 12.5 (1.3), 13.5 (sh), 19.0(1.0).

tentatively assigned an essentially square planar four-coordinate geometry, with the usual implied reservations about weak interactions from other ligands, such as the perchlorate or the solvent molecule in the remaining tetragonal sites. However, we are not sure about the conformations of the neutral tetradentate Schiff base ligands in these chelates.

Nickel (II) complexes: The nickel (II) complexes are stable in air and the analytical data (Table 1) reveal a 1 : 1 ratio of Schiff base ligand to metal salt for all of the complexes. The molar conductivity values (Table 2) support 2:1 electrolytic nature of Ni(L)X₂.nH₂O complexes in water. On the other hand, these chelates behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes in alcohol (Table 2). The deduction of electrolyte type was made by comparing the observed molar conductivities to values reported for various salts at similar concentrations,^{14,15} and for various complex ions.¹⁶

The magnetic moments of the nickel (II) complexes (Table 2) fall within the range 3.09-3.30 B.M. reported for octahedral complexes of nickel (II).¹⁷

The infrared spectra of the present ligand systems and their nickel (II) and copper (II) complexes exhibit bands typical of 2-substituted pyridines.¹⁸ These pyridine bands are the four ring stretching vibrations in the range 1610-1435 cm⁻¹, the ring breathing vibration around ~ 1000 cm⁻¹ (mixed up with ClO₄⁻ vibrations in some copper (II) chelates), and the out-of-plane C-H deformation around 790 cm⁻¹. The C=N stretching vibrations observed around 1650-1540 cm⁻¹. The positions and assignments of these bands are in agreement with those reported^{6,19,20} for FPEN and N-methylpyridine-2-carboxaldimine.

The characteristic change observed in pyridine vibrations of the ligands, together with the absence of splitting in the ring stretching modes indicate that both the pyridine moieties are coordinated^{21,22} in all the complexes. Further, the presence of C=N stretching bands in the chelates, together with the absence of NH and C=O bands (arising as a result of the partial or complete hydrolysis of the C=N band) support the Schiff base nature of the ligands.

The OH stretching bands in the complexes of FPTNOL and APTNOL and also in the complex (IX) observed in the region 3200-3550 cm⁻¹. The infrared spectral data for the nitrite and thiocyanate complexes along with tentative assignments are given in Table 4. The assignments were made by comparison to the extensive literature data for nitrite²³⁻²⁷ and thiocyanate²⁸⁻³⁰ complexes.

From the stretching frequency assignments (Table-4) the presence of oxygen-bonded NO₂ group in Ni(FPTN) (ONO)₂ (X) and Ni(APTNOL) (ONO)₂ (XV) may be inferred. The infrared frequencies observed for (X) are similar to the values reported²⁴⁻²⁷ for *trans*-[Ni(py)₄ (ONO)₂] and the analogous picoline complexes. We are unable to explain the splitting of NO₂ absorption bands observed in (XV). No bands were found for this complex which would be ascribed to the presence of non-bonded NO₂ groups,³¹ which would be present for both bridging³² and chelating²⁸ nitrite ions. The assignments of C-S stretching and NCS bending vibration in Ni (FPTNOL) (NCS)₂ (XIII) (Table-4) suggest N-bonded thiocyanate group in this chelate. Again, the splitting of the thiocyanate band is not clear to us, although it could be due to the presence of both bridging and non-bonded thiocyanate or to the presence of cis⁻, N-bonded thiocyanate ions.²⁹

TABLE 4—I. R. FREQUENCY ASSIGNMENTS FOR THE NITRITE AND THIOCYANATE IONS IN THE NICKEL (II) COMPLEXES

Ni (FPTN) (NO ₂) ₂ , (X)	Ni (APTNOL)(NO ₂) ₂ (XV)	Ni (FPTNOL)(NCS) ₂ (XIII)	Assignment
1380	1379	—	$\nu_{as}NO_2$
1150	1350 (sh)	—	$\nu_s NO_2$
820	1190	—	δNO_2
—	1155	2100	$\nu C-N$
—	821	2090	$\nu C-S$
—	—	810	δNCS
—	—	795 (sh)	
—	—	Not clearly observed.	

TABLE 5—VISIBLE AND NEAR-INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME NICKEL (II) COMPLEXES WITH ASSIGNMENTS.

Complex	Solvent	ν KK (log ϵ)	
		ν_1	ν_2
Ni (FPTN)Cl ₂ . H ₂ O, (IX)	Nujolmull	9.0, 11.98 (sh), 13.0	17.5(sh)
	H ₂ O	10.0 (sh), 12.05 (1.0), 13.2 (0.9)	18.5(8)
Ni (FPTN) (NO ₂) ₂ , (X)	Nujolmull	12.5	—
	H ₂ O	10.1 (0.5), 12.8(1.2), 13.5 (1.0)	19.0(0.9)
Ni (APTN) Cl ₂ , (XI)	H ₂ O	9.8(0.48), 12.8(0.9), 13.5 (0.9)	17.8(sh) 19.5(0.7)
	Nujolmull	11.3, 12.8 (sh)	18.6
Ni (FPTNOL)Cl ₂ , (XIII) Ni (APTNOL)Cl ₂ , (XIV)	H ₂ O	9.7(0.5), 13.0 (1.0), 13.5 (0.9)	17.6(sh) 19.5(0.6)
	Nujolmull	12.6	—
Ni (APTNOL)(NO ₂) ₂ , (XV)	H ₂ O	10.3 (0.7), 12.5 (1.3) 13.5 (sh)	19.0(1.0)

The detailed electronic absorption bands for the nickel (II) chelates are set out in Table 3, while Table 5 includes the bands in 9000-20,000 cm⁻¹ range along with their assignments. The higher-energy bands are not assigned as they may be due to various transitions, e. g., red-shifted anion transitions³³, charge-transfer transitions, ligand-transitions, and nickel (II) transitions. The bands in the 9000-20,000 cm⁻¹ range are very weak ($\epsilon \sim 10$), and has been assigned to nickel (II) d-d transitions in terms of octahedral or tetragonal configurations.^{34,35} The nujolmull and solution spectra of the nickel (II) complexes in the near-infrared and visible regions consist of two principal bands ν_1 and ν_2 (Table 5).

Splitting of the parent octahedral transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ into ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (function of in-plane donor strength) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ (function of the axial donor strength) depends on the strengths of the equatorial and axial ligands. For a series of complexes in which only the weaker axial donors are varied, the energy of the in-plane transition should remain roughly constant while the energy of the axial transition decreases in going poorer axial donors. For in-plane and axial ligands of comparable donor strength, the separation of the tetragonal levels becomes too small to be observed.

Although the number of nickel (II) bands observed in the nujolmull spectra of the present chloro-complexes

is too low to permit detailed analysis, a tentative assignment can be made using this tetragonal crystal field model assuming D_{4h} local symmetry (however, the actual symmetry may be C₂ or lower). The lowest energy component corresponds to the axial ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ transition, and the remaining more intense higher-energy component to the in-plane ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ transition.

For the nitro and thiocyanato complexes, ν_1 and ν_2 may be assigned to the ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transitions of octahedral nickel (II), and the shoulder observed on ν_1 to the spin-forbidden ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transition. The apparent lack of tetragonal splitting in ν_1 can be ascribed to the smaller difference between the planar and axial ligand field strengths.

The spectra of the present nickel (II) chelates are all approximately identical in aqueous solutions (Table 5). All of the Ni (L) X₂ complexes are formulated as 2 : 1 electrolytes in aqueous solutions (Table 2). From these observations a common species in water may be formulated as [Ni (L) (H₂O)₂]²⁺ and then the splitting of the ν_1 band (Table 5) may be explained as discussed above. The weak shoulder around 13,500 cm⁻¹ is assigned to a spin forbidden transition. It has also been observed that the splitting in ν_1 band is almost suppressed when the spectra of the aqueous solutions are taken in presence of few ml. of pyridine. This reflects the comparable donor strength of axial pyridine and the in-plane nitrogen ligands.

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